

Investigating the Influence of Infill Pattern, a Fused Deposition Process Parameter, on the Flexural Strength of PETG Parts

Nihal Pandey¹ *, Pankaj Agarwal², Ashish Manoria³

¹ *Research Scholar, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Samrat Ashok Technological Institute, Vidisha 464001, India*

² *Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Samrat Ashok Technological Institute, Vidisha 464001, India*

³ *Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Samrat Ashok Technological Institute, Vidisha 464001, India*

*Corresponding author email: nihal21mt02@satiengg.in

ABSTRACT

A wide range of applications have shown the value of additive manufacturing technologies. A well-known manufacturing technique that many industries favour for creating intricate structures affordably is fused deposition modelling (FDM). With FDM, the user can create the desired product by melting, extruding, and depositing a range of thermoplastic materials in successive layers. Similarly, the production of FDM is unaffected by design complexity. Various factors, such as layer height, build-up orientation, infill patterns are carefully taken in the process. This study examines the flexural strength of Polyethylene Terephthalate Glycol (PETG) components produced by FDM while taking into account the infill pattern process parameter and maintaining the same values for all other parameters. The infill patterns were changed to create the test samples while keeping all other factors the same. The ideal infill pattern for a more durable PETG-printed part was also investigated, as well as the flexural strength of these test specimens.

Keywords: *Additive Manufacturing (AM); Polyethylene Terephthalate Glycol (PETG); Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM); Flexural strength; Infill pattern*

1. Introduction

Rapid prototyping and 3D printing are commonly known as additive manufacturing [1], which creates a computer file based on a physical model, and then builds the thing layer by layer with powder metal, ceramic, or plastic filament. From the past, 3D printing technology has established from a mere concept in product design to a point where nearly all modern industries acknowledge its potential for future product growth. Nowadays, it is among the most commonly employed production processes across a plenty range of industries, such as automotive, medical, aerospace, food, construction, education and scientific research. 3D printing utilises a laser beam or melt nozzle to fuse certain materials, such as metal powder, ceramic powder, plastic, and other materials, and is based on a 3D computer design model created by specialised software. The molten components will then be stacked and joined layer by layer. [2]

FDM has become increasingly famous because of its low production costs, user-friendliness, and high durability of the manufactured components. Stratasys is the first company to commercialize FDM. FDM process involves the use of a nozzle of small sizes which extrudes the filament type material in a semi-molten type, depositing it onto a heated bed as a single bead, where it rapidly solidifies upon contact with the substrate or a previously placed bead. Multiple beads are deposited to create a single layer that closely matches the component's cross-section, as known as layer height. The layer which is deposited is integrate with preceding ones and then solidifies. Additionally, support filament

material is produced on demand and deposited through a secondary nozzle. Upon component completion, the support structures are removed or demolished.[3]

Initially, FDM was a straightforward process utilized for constructing building prototypes. However, it rapidly gained traction and is now widely recognized as a common manufacturing technology across almost all industries. Nevertheless, FDM has not remained stagnant and has evolved to meet new applications. Currently, FDM, as a rapid prototyping technique, is beginning to replace traditional building construction methods. FDM has numerous applications in engineering, medicine, and virtually all other fields.[4]

Srinivasan et al. [4]utilized PETG filament to produce components and conducted experimental analysis to evaluate the tensile strength of the parts, keeping all other process parameters consistent. Their findings revealed that pattern which is grid infill exhibited greatest tensile properties. Birosz et al.[5]performed bending tests on FDM samples created using three different infill patterns. They concluded that the Honeycomb and Gyroid patterns offer better mechanical resistance. Ćwikła et al. [6]analyzed different printing parameters, has shown that utilizing a honeycomb pattern can result in the production of lightweight and durable elements.. Durga Prasad Rao et al. [7]examined the tensile properties by the influence of FDM parameters on carbon-fibre polylactic acid. The study showed that a cubic infill-pattern resulted in highest tensile strength. Dev and Srivastava [8]studied the impression of printing factors and performed compressive strength test. The results indicated that the gyroid pattern exhibited good compressive strength. Srinidhi et al. [9]analyzed mechanical characteristics of various infill-patterns made using PETG and CFPETG materials. Their research found that the CFPETG sample exhibited superior characteristics, and highest strength is achieved by grid infill. Aloyaydi et al.[10]showed the compressive strength and

impact resistance of four PLA infill patterns. The highest compressive strength is shown by the grid pattern and the triangular pattern showed the highest energy absorption. Moradi et al. [11] conducted tensile and flexural tests on PLA FDM parts with different infill patterns to evaluate their mechanical responses. The investigation showed that the ultimate tensile strength was highest for the triangle infill, while the wiggle pattern resulted in greater flexibility. Zaman et al. [12] performed the compressive strength test of FDM process-parameters. Based on analysis, the diamond-shaped infill pattern demonstrated an optimal condition. Yadav et al. [13] carried out research on the compressive properties of FDM-printed PLA parts with six infill-patterns. The study concluded that the Hilbert-curve infill pattern demonstrated the highest compressive properties among all the designs. Dave et al. [14] investigated tensile strength using FDM printed items with various infill patterns. They found that stacking layers parallel to the same direction is more effective than multiple infill patterns for 0° raster orientation.

After conducting a thorough analysis, a few infill patterns with minimal infill density were selected for further testing. Test specimens were created using several infill patterns, including tri-hexagon, cubic subdivision, quarter cubic, zig zag, among others, according to the optimal specifications. The flexural strength of these test samples was then evaluated using a Universal Testing Machine (UTM) at CIPET (Bhopal). The study concluded that the highest infill-pattern for optimal parameters with minimal infill density was identified.

2. Materials and Process

2.1 Material

This study is centered on the use of FDM technology with PETG as the printing material. PETG is a copolymer commonly used in 3D printing and is made by copolymerizing PET

with a colorless or clear glycol. [15]. $(C_{10}H_8O_4)_n$ is the chemical composition of PETG. In the field of manufacturing, PETG is a copolymer that is widely used and compatible with FDM. PETG has excellent bending and tensile strength and is utilized in various applications such as liquid containers, engineering resin and fiber clothing when combined with glass fiber. Its remarkable features include chemical resilience and durability[16].

2.2 Process Parameters

The objective of this research is to explore the impact of altering the infill pattern while maintaining consistent parameters, including infill density, layer thickness and print speed, among other factors.

In the process of developing each layer, the infill pattern plays a crucial role in providing internal support to the 3D print. The presence of an infill pattern is essential since material incline to sag in vacant gaps in the print, which can lead to printing issues [4]. The infill patterns chosen for this investigation include tri-hexagon, cubic subdivision, quarter cubic, zigzag, cross and cross 3D, as shown in Fig. 1. (a-f).

Fig. 1. (a-f). Selected infill patterns

Layer height refers to the thickness of each layer as well as the vertical axis step performed prior to extruding a new layer above the preceding layer.

Infill Density is a percentage that shows how much plastic is used in the 3D print.

Build-up orientation is the location of the item or sample at the start of production.

Print speed is the number of millimetres that the print head moves in one second.

2.3 Process

FDM is vigorously used & reliable 3D printing technique. The process, as shown in Figure 2, entails melting the filament or material, extruding it from the small nozzle and depositing it layer-by-layer onto the print bed.

Fig. 2. Fused Deposition Modelling Process

The fabrication procedure was carried out using the Divide by Zero printer's Aion 500 MK2 as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Aion 500 MK2 (Divide by Zero) printer.

The specimen was developed with CATIA software, and Fig. 4 shows the CAD model.

Fig. 4. CAD deign Flexural Specimen.

Once the CAD file is prepared, it is exported as a.STL file and then imported into a slicing software such as Ultimaker CURA. In the slicing software, the user optimizes the printing parameters. Once the parameters are set, the sliced file is transferred to the 3D printer and printer is configured for starting the printof the part.

2.4 Specimen Fabrication

For this investigation, flexural specimens were printed using the FDM technique on an Aion 500 MK2 3D printer. The specimens were made in accordance with American Society for Testing & Materials (ASTM) standard D790, as illustrated in Fig. 5. Fig. 6 depicts the constructed part. The process parameters evaluated thus far for fabrication are listed in Table

1.

Fig.5. Schematic model of the required specimen

Fig. 6. Printed Specimens

Table 1. : Process parameters and values

S.No.	Infill Pattern	Layer Height (mm)	Infill Density
1.	Tri-Hexagon	0.1	50 %
2.	Cubic Subdivision		
3.	Quarter Cubic		
4.	Zig Zag		
5.	Cross		
6.	Cross 3D		

3. Experiment

Flexural strength is a material's capacity to resist the bending forces applied perpendicular to its longitudinal-axis. Due to the flexural load, a combination of compressive and tensile stresses are induced [17] . A material's flexural characteristics must be determined before it can be used to manufacture any part. The flexural test was conducted utilizing a Universal Testing Machine (UTM) as shown in the Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Universal Testing Machine (UTM).

4. Result and discussion

After each sample has undergone the requisite testing, the experimental results are recorded in table 2. Figure 8 illustrates the correlation between infill pattern and flexural strength.

Table 2: Chosen infill-patterns with their flexural strength.

S.No.	Infill Pattern	Average Flexural Strength (MPa)
1.	Tri-Hexagon	58.76
2.	Cubic Subdivision	55.45
3.	Quarter Cubic	41.06
4.	Zig Zag	57.09

5.	Cross	56.38
6.	Cross 3D	60.57

Fig. 8. Flexural Strength vs. Infill Pattern.

Among the tested configurations, the cross 3D infill pattern, with a 50 % infill density and a layer height of 0.1 mm, exhibited the highest flexural strength, measuring at 60.57 MPa. When comparing infill patterns with identical infill density and layer height, it was found that the tri-hexagon pattern demonstrated the second highest flexural strength, reaching 58.76 MPa. Among the six infill patterns, the quarter cubic pattern has the lowest impact strength with 41.06 Mpa. After the quarter cubic pattern, the cubic subdivision and cubic cross infill patterns have the lowest flexural strength, at 55.45 and 56.38 Mpa, respectively. Therefore, a

cross 3D infill pattern is preferable for better results when 3D printing with PETG (Transparent) material using the FDM technique.

5. Conclusion

The study conducted an experimental analysis to determine the flexural strength of PETG filament components by evaluating the impact of various infill patterns on FDM process parameters while maintaining all other parameters constant.

- The cross 3D infill pattern produced greater flexural strength than any other infill pattern.
- The maximum flexural strength reported using a cross 3D pattern was 60.57 Mpa.
- Quarter Cubic infill pattern has a minimum flexural strength value of 41.06 Mpa.
- The infill pattern process parameters also influence the flexural strength of FDM produced items.

Based on the aforementioned findings, it can be concluded that the cross 3D infill pattern, with a lower infill percentage and a consistent layer height, provides higher flexural strength. The wastage of material can be reduced and a higher strength can be achieved by using the appropriate infill pattern.

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